

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW AND STUDY OF MATRICARIA CHAMOMILLA

¹Mr. K. Naveen kumar, ¹Mr. B. Meswanthran, ¹Mr. Dhanush,
¹Mr. S. Umesh, ²Mrs. T. Manjula

¹P. S. V College Of Pharmaceutical Science And Research, Krishnagiri- 635108, Tamil Nadu

²Associate Professor, Department Of Pharmaceutical Analysis,

P. S. V College Of Pharmaceutical Science And Research, Krishnagiri- 635108, Tamil Nadu

Abstract:

The well-known medicinal plant species chamomile (Matricaria chamomilla L.), which belongs to the Asteraceae family, is frequently mentioned to as the "star among medicinal species." It originated in Western Asia and Europe and has now spread to other nations. Traditional and folk medicines all around the world have been using plant extracts and essential oils for thousands of years. There is a live domestic (Indian) and worldwide market for chamomile that is growing daily. Assam, Uttar Pradesh, and Jammu & Kashmir are the main growing regions for chamomile. More than 120 components are present in the plant. A wide range of industries, including the food, cosmetics, and pharmaceutical sectors, used chamomile. The study aims to present the botanical characteristics, geographic range, traditional applications, chemical components, pharmacological properties, cultivation methods, toxicity tests, and quality control measures. Oils, sterols, triterpenes, flavonoids, saponins, tannins, alkaloids, glycosides, proteins, mucins, sesquiterpenes, coumarins, polyacetylenes, phenyl carboxylic acids, amino acids, phytosterols, choline, and mineral compounds were all present in Matricaria chamomilla. Terpenoids, including chamazulene, bisabolol, farnesene and its oxides A and B are the main constituents of essential oils. The essential oils and extracts of M. chamomilla have demonstrated significant anti-inflammatory, antifungal, antidepressant, antipyretic, anti-allergic, anticancer, antidiabetic, antiparasitic, antioxidant, and analgesic properties.

Corresponding author:

T. Manjula,

Associate Professor, Department Of Pharmaceutical Analysis,

P. S. V College Of Pharmaceutical Science And Research,

Krishnagiri- 635108, Tamil Nadu

QR CODE

Please cite this article in press T. Manjula et al., A Comprehensive Review And Study Of Matricaria Chamomilla., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12(08).

INTRODUCTION:

Matricaria chamomilla originates in southern and eastern Europe and is one of the most important medicinal plants. It is also grown in Hungary, Brazil, Germany, France, Russia, and Yugoslavia. It was brought to India in the Mughal Empire and is currently grown in Maharashtra, Punjab, Uttar Pradesh, and Jammu & Kashmir. Greece, Rome, and ancient Egypt have all employed it for thousands of years. Currently, this plant is listed in the pharmacopoeia of 26 different nations. The family Asteraceae includes *Matricaria chamomilla* L. synonym *Matricaria recutita* L. Oils, sterols, sesquiterpenes, flavonoids, coumarins, triterpenes, saponins, tannins, alkaloids, sugars, proteins, amino acids, phenyl carboxylic acids, polyacetylenes, phyosterols, mucins, choline, and mineral compounds were all found in *Matricaria chamomilla*. Over 120 components have been found in the phytochemical makeup of *Matricaria chamomilla* essential oil and extracts.

Many secondary metabolites, including flavonoids like apigenin, luteolin, and quercetin, and terpenoids like bisabolol and its oxides A and B, bisabolone oxide A, chamazulene, and farnesene, are found in herbs and are useful as food additives, biopesticides, agrochemicals, flavors, fragrances, and colors. The pharmacological studies demonstrated that *Matricaria chamomilla* had anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, antidiabetic, antidiarrheal, antiparasitic, antimicrobial, antidepressant, antispasmodic, sedative, hypotensive, anxiolytic, analgesic, reproductive, antiulcerogenic, protective, anticonvulsant, hypolipidemic, memory-enhancing, and many other effects. The blue essential oil, with a concentration ranging from 0.2% to 1.9%, is present in *Matricaria chamomilla* flowers.

The volatile oil is present in the plant stem, leaves, and even root, even though the concentration is higher and the active chemicals are richer in the flowers. Reaching a height of 30 to 60 cm, the leaves of this annual branching plant are finely split. For about 200 years, the plant has been

cultivated in Lucknow, India. In the Mughal Empire, it was brought to Punjab some 300 years ago. In India right now, there is no need for blue oil in general. Chamomile is a plant that is commonly grown in Europe and has been brought to certain Asian countries for the manufacture of its essential oil, but its blossoms are always in high demand. It is mostly used internally as a tisane for stomach pain, slow digestion, diarrhea, and nausea; it is also used infrequently but very successfully for urinary tract irritation and uncomfortable menstruation. The powdered medication can be given externally to chronic wounds that take a long time to heal, skin eruptions, infections including boils and shingles, hemorrhoids, and inflammation of the eyes, mouth, and throat. The flower heads contain an essential oil that contains azulene and is utilized in hair preparations, teeth pastes, cosmetic creams, skin lotions, perfumery, and dye liquors. It is an annual plant that blooms from June to September in India. This perennial herb can be grown in any kind of soil and can withstand cold temperatures.

TAXONOMY:**1. BASIC CLASSIFICATION:**

Kingdom: Plantae Family : Asteraceae

Order : Asterales

Clade : Angiosperms

Genus : *Matricaria*

Species : *chamomilla*

2. DETAILED CLASSIFICATION:

Kingdom : Plantae

Class : Magnoliopsida

Subclass : Asteridae

Super Division : Spermatophyta

Division : Magnoliophyta

Family : Asteraceae

Order : Asterales

Genus : *Matricaria*

MORPHOLOGY:

The flower heads have a diameter of 10 to 30 mm and are heterogamous and pedunculate. Their golden yellow, 1.5-2.5 mm long, five-toothed tubular florets are arranged independently and invariably end in a glandulous tube. Due to the blue essential oil they contain, the blossoms have a distinct scent and set of traits. The roots become spindle-shaped and grow straight. The growth range of the stems is 10 to 80 cm. True chamomile is an annual with thin, spindly roots that only penetrate the ground if it is flat. Eleven to twenty-seven plants have concentrically clustered white flowers that are 6 to 11 mm long and 3.5 mm wide. One reason for the decreased salt content of the top soil is the relatively extensive sodium deposition of the plants (66 mg/100 gram of dry material). The characteristics of the plants that were planted between Finland and Hungary, 1500 kilometers

apart, did not differ much. Finland has lower temperatures than Hungary, thus the essential oil has less of the oxide kind. Climates that have temperatures between 7 and 26 degrees Celsius and 400 to 1400 millimeters of precipitation annually might be conducive to cultivation. As the “star among medicinal species,” the well-known medicinal plant *Matricaria chamomilla* L. belongs to the Asteraceae family. In addition to English chamomile, they are also known as German chamomile, Hungarian chamomile, Roman chamomile, and chamomile. The genus *Anthemis*, especially the poisonous and odorous *Anthemis cotula* L., is frequently mistaken for authentic chamomile. It is a yellowish-brown cypsela with three to five weak ribs. Even though *Matricaria chamomilla* can be grown in any type of soil, rich, heavy, and damp soils should be avoided. For optimal EO yield, the plant requires long summer days and high temperatures, but it can withstand freezing temperatures. Naturally allogamous, it exhibits extensive segregation and blooms in the second week of March.

GEOGRAPHICAL DISTRIBUTION:

Throughout Europe (Hungary, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Switzerland, France, Albania, Russian Federation-European part, Belgium, Slovakia, Bulgaria, Sweden, Czech Republic, Romania, Austria, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Belarus, Greece, Spain, Italy, Ukraine, Slovenia, Serbia, United Kingdom, Norway, and Montenegro), Asia (China, India, Russian Federation, Cyprus, Mongolia, Iraq, Afghanistan, Iran, Palestine, Syria, Turkey, Uzbekistan, Azerbaijan, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Georgia, and Lebanon), and Africa (Algeria and Morocco) it is widely grown.

Hungary produces a large amount of chamomile biomass, especially in regions with low soils, which benefits the local economy. Flowers are imported into Germany in order to extract oil. Brazil also grows it, as do Yugoslavia, France, Russia, and others. Currently grown in Jammu & Kashmir, Maharashtra, Uttar Pradesh, and Punjab, it was first brought to India in the Mughal Empire. Originally utilized in ancient Greece, Egypt, and Rome, chamomile has been used for thousands of years as a herbal remedy. The lord had given the Anglo-Saxons nine sacred herbs, and this was one of them. “Chamomile is an ingredient in many traditional, Unani, and homeopathic medicinal preparations and is listed in the pharmacopoeia of 26 countries.”

CULTIVATION:

SOIL AND CLIMATIC REQUIREMENTS

Any kind of soil can be used to grow German chamomile, although it is best to avoid using rich,

heavy, and moist soils. With temperatures between 2°C and 20°C, it can also tolerate low temperatures. At the Regional Research Laboratory’s farm in Jammu, the crop has been produced with great success on loamy sand soils. At the National Botanical Research Institute’s Banthra farm in Lucknow, the crop has thrived on soil that has a pH of 9. The pH range of 9 to 9.2 is said to be favorable for its growth. It thrives widely in Hungary on clayey lime soils, which are arid areas deemed unsuitable for any other crop. The ideal temperature range for seed germination is 10°C to 20°C. This crop is 4elsius4y sensitive to the season. In India, chamomile can be grown up to 2000m above sea level as a summer crop on hills and as a winter crop in plains. In the hills of North India, this Rabi crop is sown during the second two weeks of December; in the lowlands, it is sown in late September or early October. Chamomile is a crop that grows from December to April and is considered a winter crop. Due to its subtropical climate, southern India can sustain chamomile cultivation, particularly in areas with cool, dry winters like Bangalore, Ooty, and Kodaikanal, which occur in the range of 10 to 25°C. The second week of March is when chamomile begins to bloom, and three manual flower pickings can be done at intervals of seven to ten days.

PROPAGATION

Seeds are used to spread the plant. The crop’s seeds are little; a thousand of them weigh between 0.088 and 0.153 grams. When seeded in an area of 200–250 m², 0.3-0.5 kg of clean seed with a good germination rate produces enough seedlings to stock a hectare of land. There are two ways to cultivate the crop: direct seeding and transplanting. For direct seeding, the field must have ideal moisture conditions; otherwise, spotty and subpar germination results. The transplanting approach is typically used since direct seeding typically produces poor germination. When transplanting, the seedlings’ mortality rate is essentially zero. The optimum temperature range for effective seed germination is 10 to 20 degree 4elsius. Compost and high-quality farmyard manure (FYM) were applied to nursery beds, which were then kept moist. September, shortly after the end of the monsoon season in North India, is the best time of year to produce seedlings in a nursery. Within four to five days of seeding, germination begins, and within four to five weeks, the seedlings are prepared for transplantation. Transplanting seedlings that are more than five weeks old will produce a poor and uninteresting yield. The ideal sowing time and technique were examined using the thermal model. According to the study, transplanting the crop was better than direct seeding, and the optimal period for transplanting the crop to achieve higher yields was October 10–

18. Delays in transplantation should not exceed the end of October.

CROP GROWTH

Crop growth slows until the middle of January and then progressively accelerates until the beginning of February. Crop growth is highly active as the season warms up (increases in height, branching, and bud creation), and stray flowers may appear in the crop. Because there is a lot of bud development in March, the plants grow all around, and the early-formed buds blossom into flowers, the harvesting of flowers must also be selected throughout the crop cycle. The crop will experience heavy seed-setting and plant maturity if the temperature rises suddenly from 33°C to 39°C in a matter of days. Seeds shed, and a crop that germinates on its own the following year is seen.

IRRIGATION

For optimum growth, chamomile requires irrigation once a week due to its weak roots. Less water is required by heavier soils than by lighter ones. Irrigation for sandy loam should take place every four to five days, contingent on the weather. Because the crop has shallow roots. The quantity of flowers is increased by frequent irrigation during the flowering or rosette phase. They also mentioned the need for frequent irrigation—roughly six to eight times per crop cycle on alkaline soils. The effects of various plant spacing and irrigation treatments (5, 10, 15, 20, and 25 cm intra-row with 30 cm inter-row) were examined. With irrigation set at 50 mm evaporation and 10 cm between rows, the best results were obtained, yielding the most biomass, seeds, essential oil, and dried flowers.

MANURES AND FERTILIZERS

While the effects of potassium and phosphorus are minimal, nitrogen has a significant impact on the production of fresh flowers and oil. Dutta and Singh found that while the oil concentration dropped from 0.64 to 0.59%, the application of Nitrogen in the form of ammonium sulfate at 40 kg/hectare greatly boosted the yield of fresh flowers and oil. Crop performance is enhanced when organic matter is added because it raises the soil's humus content. El-Hamidi et al. recommend a 2:2 N2 to P ratio in order to maximize yield. The chamazulene % significantly decreased when Nitrogen was applied at a higher level. Paun and Mihalopa discovered that enough crop growth was caused by applying 50 kg/hectare of phosphorus and potassium each in the fall before to planting and 50 kg/hectare of Nitrogen in the early spring. Nevertheless, the content of chamazulene and volatile oil remained unaffected. Singh discovered that plants responded well to Nitrogen and Phosphorus fertilizers in saline alkaline soils.

According to Misra and Kapoor, the ideal Nitrogen and Phosphorus dosages were 50–60 kg N/hectare and 50 kg P₂O₅/hectare. According to reports, Nitrogen considerably reduced the amounts of bisabolol oxides A and B in the essential oil while greatly increasing the amounts of α -bisabolol and chamazulene. Nitrogen considerably raised the output of essential oils per unit dry flower weight in both the Tisane and Bohemia types.

WEED CONTROL

Approximately three to four hoeings and weedings are necessary to produce a healthy crop. One comprehensive weeding and hoeing one month after planting is adequate for crops growing in saline alkaline soils. Wiatkowski et al. from Poland found that using the bioproducts Bio Algeen and Herbagreen Basic reduced the annual weed density in organic chamomile cultivation by about 20% as compared to the control. Additionally, broader row spacing (40 cm) produced more weed biomass than narrower row spacing (30 cm), indicating that crop geometry has a significant effect on weed infestation. According to Frabboni et al. (2019), oregano (*Origanum vulgare* L.) and rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis* L.) essential oils were sprayed three times during the chamomile crop cycle at two concentrations are undiluted and 50% diluted. They found that using the undiluted essential oil treatment increased the effectiveness of weed management. "An additional study discovered that a good control of weeds was achieved by applying sodium salt of 2,4-D (2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid) at 1.0 to 1.5 kg/ha following four weeks of transplanting."

HARVESTING

Harvesting the chamomile flower at the medium flower ripening stage will preserve the essential oil in the medication for a longer period of time. Beginning in the second two weeks of February and lasting until the middle of April, flowering takes place. Flowers that are fully opened should be harvested right away because delaying harvesting could cause seeds to shed. Individual selection Flowers can be made by hand or with the use of skippers or flower scoops. Four to five harvests could be taken at intervals of ten to fifteen days. The third or fourth flush of blossoming will yield the most flowers. The plant itself will be permitted to produce seeds during the fifth flush of flowers. The crop yields 60 q/ha of fresh flowers and 10–15 q/ha of dry flowers. The crop did well in Bangalore conditions as well. With closer spacing of 30 × 20 cm, it produced fresh flower yields of 6.09 tonnes/hectare and dried flower yields of 1.64 tonnes/hectare, respectively. "It produced a 6.36 kg/hectare essential oil yield."

DISEASES AND PESTS

It has been claimed that the chamomile crop is attacked by a variety of insects, fungus, and viruses. *Puccinia anthemidis*, *Phytophthora cactorum*, *Peronospora leptosperma*, *Puccinia matricariae*, *Peronospora radii*, *Cylindrosporium matricariae*, *Halicobasidium purpureum*, *Erysiphe cichoracearum*, *E. polyphage*, *Albugo tragopogonis*, *Sphaerotheca macularis*, and *Septoria chamomillae* are known to attack this plant. This plant is also severely harmed by the yellow virus. A 0.1% benlate spray was used to control the illness. Black bean aphids were feeding on *Matricaria chamomilla*, according to Fluister. The plant's defoliation is induced by *Autographa chryson*, while the insect *Nysius minor* sheds *Matricaria chamomilla* blossoms. The aphid infestation on chamomile was well managed with a single spray of 0.2% fosfotion treatment. Methyl bromide worked well as a fumigant to combat *Ephestia elutella* insect infestation in the dried chamomile herb. *Metalydacolus longistriatus* was discovered to be connected to chamomile roots in the Egypt. In addition to harming the chamomile crop, fungi and insects also severely harm the dried flowers while they are being stored, lowering the quality of the dried raw product. This is due to the high concentration of hydrophilic components (flavonoids, sugars, amino acids, phenyl carbonic acids, mucilages, choline, and salts) in dried chamomile, especially the flowers, as well as the hygroscopic nature of chamomile plants. It takes very little time for fungal agents to cause microbiological degradation.

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENT:

Matricaria chamomilla also known as german chamomilla. It contains variety of chemical constituents with essential oil with main components include sesquiterpenoids like α -bisabolol, chamazulene and β -farnesene, coumarins and phenolic acids.

SESQUITERPENOID α -BISABOLOL

Bisabolol, a sesquiterpene alcohol, was first isolated from *Materia chamomilla* in the 20th century. Since the US Food and Drug Administration has classified bisabolol as a generally recognized chemical due to its low toxicity, it can be used as an active ingredient in a wide range of commercial products. Notably, bisabolol has been shown to have anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antibacterial, anticancer, antiseptic, and skin-smoothing properties.

CHAMAZULEN

The essential oil of *matricaria chamomilla* contains chamazulene, a naturally occurring chemical compound that is a sesquiterpene. It is the main ingredient that gives the plant its therapeutic effect against weed species like *persicaria lapathifolia*,

Stellaria medium, *Sonchus aleraceus*, *amaranthus chlorostachys*, *Cirsium arvense*, and *Chenopodium album*. It has shown potent herbicidal and phytotoxic effects.

B-FARNESENE

Commercial synthesis of β -farnesene, a sesquiterpenoid with numerous industrial applications, is carried out using engineered strains of *Sacchromyces cerevisiae*. The antioxidant activities in vitro using the DPPH test have demonstrated that β -farnesene has antimicrobial potential and antioxidant free radical scavenging activity. Studies have also shown that β -farnesene enriched extracts have strong antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and other gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria, as well as that they are sensitive to the strong antibacterial activity of *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus epidermidis*.

BISABOLOL OXIDE

It has been discovered that many bisabolol oxide derivatives are present in the methanol extract of German chamomile flower heads. When n-butanol and ethyl acetate fractions were combined, 15 hydroxybisabolol oxide A and β -D glucoside 5 were produced, whereas the n-hexane fraction produced 9 hydroxybisabolol oxide A1, seco bisabolol oxide B2, 1-hydroxy bisabolol oxide B3, and bisabolol oxide A glucoside 4.

PHENOLIC COMPOUNDS FLOVONOIDS

The extract of *Matricaria chamomilla* is rich in flavonoids and their glycoside derivatives. *Matricaria chamomilla* aerial portions had total flavonoid concentrations ranging from 0.82 to 36.75g of quercetin equivalent (QE)/100g of dry material.

QUERCETIN

Quercetin is a nutraceutical that can be used to treat a number of illness. Its positive effects on redox and cell signal transmission pathways are the main reasons it is useful in the treatment and prevention of human disease. Quercetin produces antioxidant and anti-inflammatory actions.

APIGENIN

Apigenin, also known by its chemical name 4,5,7-trihydroxyflavone, is a naturally occurring component of the flavone family with a molecular weight of 270.24. It is an aglycone derivative of many naturally occurring glucosides. There are numerous pharmacological effects of apigenin and its synthetic flavone derivatives, such as antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antiallergic, anticancer, antiproliferative, and neuroprotective qualities.

COUMARINS

Coumarin is derived from the parent nucleus benzopyrone. According to research, chamomile contains 10 distinct coumarins, including methoxycoumarin, 3,4-dihydrocoumarin, daphnetin, scopoletin, daphnetin, daphnin, umbelliferone, and skimming.

HERNIARIN

It is a naturally occurring coumarin derivative that is present in a variety of plant species and is chemically known as 7-methoxycoumarin. Herniarin produces anti-inflammatory and antioxidant action. Anti cytotoxicity properties significant chemoprotection against cisplatin included genotoxicity is another effect of herniarin.

UMBELLIFERONE

Matricaria chamomilla contains a coumarin component called umbelliferone. Its scientific name is 7-hydroxycoumarin, and it can be found in a variety of plant species, including golden apples, bitter oranges, carrots, and chamomile. The largest amount of herniarin and umbelliferone was obtained by using a maceration method with a 50% aqueous ethanol solution. Umbelliferone and herniarin are two known metabolites of stress. Umbelliferone has nephroprotective capabilities as well as anti-inflammatory, anti-umorigenic, and antioxidant qualities.

PHENOLIC ACID CHLOROGENIC ACID

Chlorogenic acid is another interesting phenolic phytochemical that was identified in *matricaria chamomilla*. It is also found in coffee, chrysanthemum, honeysuckle, Hawthorn, and eucommia. An important antioxidant present in *matricaria chamomilla* extract, chlorogenic acid, has been shown to protect cells from oxidative damage and lipid peroxidation. It has also been shown to lower left ventricular diastolic stiffness and lower elevated systolic blood pressure. This is most likely because inflammatory cell infiltration is prevented and collagen protein deposition is reduced.

CAFFEIC ACID

Caffeic acid is another medicinal phytochemical found in Acid Caffeine *Matricaria chamomilla*. With a minimum inhibitory concentration ranging from 256 µg/ml to 1024 µg/ml, caffeine exhibits strong antibacterial activity against *S. aureus* strains and has been shown in numerous in vitro and in vivo studies to be an effective treatment agent for a variety of malignancies. Additionally, it generates antiviral characteristics.

PHARMACOLOGICAL EFFECT: ANTI INFLAMMATORY EFFECT

When administered intraperitoneally to rats, *Matricaria chamomilla* (at 1/10 LD₅₀ doses of 80% ethanol extracts) greatly reduced the paw edema caused by carrageenan. The anti-inflammatory properties of *Matricaria chamomilla* aqueous extract (300 and 500 mg/kg) were investigated in mice with experimental trauma-induced hind paw edema and carrageenan. In both animals, the aqueous extract of *Matricaria chamomilla* exhibited strong anti-inflammatory properties that were on par with the control. Rats' xylene-induced inflammations and acetic acid-induced inflammatory pain models were used to examine the hydroalcoholic extract (500, 1000, and 1500 mg/kg body weight) of *Matricaria chamomilla* capitolis have anti-inflammatory and analgesic properties. At 1500 mg/kg BW, the extract dramatically decreased the rats' xylene-induced inflammation.

At 500, 1000, and 1500 mg/kg Body Weight, the extract also considerably decreased the inflammatory discomfort brought on by acetic acid. Topically, the anti-inflammatory effects of the ethanolic chamomile solution and the raw ethanolic chamomile extract were examined. 1.0% carbopol 940 gel formulations were made using extract concentrations of 3.0% and 5.0%. The permeability enhancer in gelling formulations was sodium lauryl sulfate. The rats' epidermis was treated with the formulations after carrageenan caused paw edema.

Matricaria chamomilla's main flavonoids, apigenin, quercetin, and luteolin, each has a distinct mechanism of action for its anti-inflammatory and anti-gout properties. Apigenin demonstrated anti-inflammatory properties by preventing the generation of proinflammatory cytokines, whereas luteolin inhibited the synthesis of prostaglandin E₂, nitric oxide, and the expression of cyclooxygenase-2 and inducible nitric oxide synthase. Inhibiting LTB₄ production and arachidonic acid peroxidation, chamazulene also had antioxidant properties and decreased inflammatory mediators. As a result, *Matricaria chamomilla* can reduce rheumatoid arthritis discomfort and inflammation.

ANTIOXIDANT EFFECT

Antioxidants inhibit the chemical process of oxidation, which can generate free radicals. Degradation of organic compounds, including living things, is caused by anti-oxidation. Antioxidant-rich diets may reduce the risk of heart disease, several types of cancer, and other illnesses. The potential of the chamomile flower essential oil to scavenge free 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radicals was determined using the 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl assay in order to

examine the antioxidant activity of the isolated chamomile flowers. After dissolving the essential oil from chamomile flowers in ethanol, a series of different concentrations were produced. Immediately following the DPPH radical, absorbance at 517 nm was recorded at 20, 30, 60, and 90 minutes of incubation.

ANTICANCER EFFECT

Gliomas are prevalent malignant tumors that develop quickly, have a high recurrence rate, a high mortality rate, and a poor prognosis. Chamomile essential oil contains α bisabolol, a fat-soluble sesquiterpene molecule that has been shown to have the ability to influence gliomas. Yanetal. used the scratch assay to investigate the effect of α bisabolol on human brain glioma cells (U251 and U87). It was examined how it affected invasion and migration. Western blot has been used in protein expression research. Glioblastoma cell movement and invasion were reduced by α bisabolol through downregulating central mucocutaneous tumor (c Met). α Bisabolol oxide A and apigenin 7- β -D-glucoside, which are extracted from chamomile stems and flowers, have been shown to deactivate the vascular epidermal growth factor receptor 2 angiogenic enzymes and prevent the migration of Caco 2 colon cancer cells. This plant contains apigenin, a flavonoid that has some anticancer properties against leukemia cells and liver cancer cells. In addition, apigenin 7-O-glycoside derived from chamomile extract was found to have a favorable anticancer effect by Srivastava et al., but this effect was not as strong as that of apigenin.

ANTIDEPRESSANT EFFECT

Aromatherapy using essential oils is seen as an alternative therapy for depression. When depressed people experience both bodily and psychological suffering, chamomile is a great way to help. An innovative approach to treating depression is provided by the effective relief of postpartum women's sleep patterns and depressed symptoms by chamomile tea prepared from chamomile flower heads. Chamomile may have antidepressant properties, according to some pharmacological studies. In the rat brain, for instance, isobaric tag for relative and absolute quantification and polymerase chain reaction study revealed that the plant's α -pinene increased the expression of proteins linked to oxidative phosphorylation and parvalbumin mRNA.

GASTROPROTECTIVE EFFECT

A promising gastroprotective plant for flatulence, stomachaches, spasms, and reduced gastric output is chamomile. When ethanol causes stomach mucosal damage in rats, its extract shows antioxidant and antiulcer properties. Protecting

gastric sulfhydryl groups, raising GSH levels, decreasing MDA levels, and counteracting the effects of intracellular mediators, including calcium, hydrogen peroxide, and free iron, are the mechanisms behind gastroprotective actions.

ANTIDIARRHEAL AND ANTISPASMODIC EFFECT

In traditional Tunisian medicine and TC medicine, chamomile is extensively used to treat diarrhea and spasticity. Children's acute diarrhea can be effectively treated in Germany with this plant's extract, which lessens symptoms and shortens the illness's duration. Mehmood et al. used isolated rabbit jejunum to report the antispasmodic and antidiarrheal properties of chamomile. The extract from chamomile decreases Ca^{2+} antagonism and opens K^{+} channels. HichemSebai documented the extract's positive benefits on castor oil-induced diarrhea, lowering MDA levels and antioxidant enzyme activity. Furthermore, the apigenin and apigenin in chamomile have a potent antispasmodic action on smooth muscle.

ANTIPARASITIC EFFECT

The ability of *Matricaria chamomilla* Essential oil and extracts to stop the growth of a variety of insects and parasites has been the subject of numerous investigations. The leishmanicidal efficacy of Tunisian *Matricaria chamomilla* Eos was assessed in vitro. The findings indicated that Eos demonstrated good activity on the extracellular and motile promastigotes of *Leishmania amazonensis* (Inhibitory Concentration 50=10.8 g/mL after 96 hours) and *Leishmania infantum* (Inhibitory Concentration 50=10.4 g/mL after 96 hours), whereas bisabolol was able to trigger the promastigote programmed cell death effects. The activity of bisabolol against *Acanthamoeba castellanii* has been examined in another investigation by Hajaji et al. With Inhibitory Concentration 50 = 20.83 g/mL and Inhibitory Concentration 90 = 46.60 g/mL, the results demonstrated that bisabolol possesses amoebicidal action. It also shown the ability to decrease ATP levels and increase the permeability of the plasmatic membrane.

The insecticidal activity against fruit flies (*Drosophila melanogaster*), the larvicidal activity against glass worms (*Chaoborus plumicornis*), and the nematocidal activity against *Artemia salina* and *Caenorhabditis elegans* were all evaluated for *Matricaria chamomilla* essential oil from Nepal. These organisms did not exhibit any toxicity, according to the data.

ANTIDIABETIC EFFECT

The anti-maltase and anti-amylase properties of *Matricaria chamomilla* extract, purified apigenin-

7-O- glucoside, apigenin, and cis -2-hydroxy-4-methoxycinnamic acid glucosides and trans-2-hydroxy-4- methoxycinnamic acid glucosides have been evaluated. The chemicals and extract both shown a concentration- dependent suppression of both enzyme activities, according to results. Apigenin-7-O-glucoside, and apigenin respectively produced the high levels of maltase and amylase inhibition. Moreover, these two flavonoids had the capacity to control sugar absorption and limit the transfer of glucose and sucrose. Furthermore, a different investigation found that the hydro-methanolic extract of *Matricaria chamomilla* and a few isolated chemicals suppressed the activity of aldose reductase in rat lenses. Furthermore, 3,5-O-di-caffeoylquinic acid and luteolin- 7-O-D-glucuronide inhibited the production of advanced glycation end products, whereas luteolin and luteolin-7- O-D-glucuronide inhibited the accumulation of sorbitol in rat lenses under high-glucose circumstances. Moreover, the ethanolic extract of *M.chamomilla* showed anti-glycation

qualities with an Inhibitory Concentration 50 of 264.2 g/mL for lipase inhibition performance.

ANTIMICROBIAL EFFECT

Microbiological activity Essential oil and several extracts of *Matricaria chamomilla* made using solvent with varying polarity, such as ethanol, methanol, hexane, and diethyl ether were evaluated against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Salmonella coli* O157, and *Candida albicans*. When compared to plant extracts that inhibited bacteria with Minimum Inhibitory Concentration values ranging from 10-17.5 µg/mL, essential oils often had Minimum Inhibitory Concentration values in the lower range of 10-12.5 µg/mL. The essential oil of the plant was abundant in α -bisabolol, α -bisabolol oxide A, and α -bisabolol oxide B. By preventing the synthesis of ergosterol, α -Bisabolol may prevent the growth of fungi. Generally speaking, chamomile essential oil exhibited bacteriostatic action, particularly against gram-positive bacteria.

TOXICITY AND SIDE EFFECTS:

The high level of safety linked to chamomile use was demonstrated by a number of animal studies. In one particular toxicity study using rabbit models, the acute oral LD50 and acute cutaneous LD50 were determined to be greater than 5 g/kg body weight. The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has classified German chamomile oil and extract as chemicals Generally Regarded As Safe (GRAS). Unfavorable Safety Events Atopic and contact dermatitis have been linked to chamomile consumption in a few case reports. Some people who have ragweed, chrysanthemum, or other aster allergies also have chamomile allergies. Cases of chamomile eye washes resulting in allergic conjunctivitis have been documented.

Although the plant was generally healthy to eat, *Matricaria chamomilla* should be used with caution by those who are hypersensitive to ragweed and other Compositae plants. There have been few reports of allergic reactions to chamomile, and the plant has no known harmful substances. Before and after the trials, the leukocytes' vitality was greater than 95%, and the primary screening tests using all tested concentrations of *Chamomilla recutita* extracts revealed no evidence of cytotoxicity to the human leukocytes.

USES:

Chamomilla recutita flower heads' essential oils have flavoring and coloring qualities that have led to their widespread use in the industry for commercial products such as hair products, ointments, beverages, perfumes, lotions, detergents, soaps, confections, herbal teas, and baked goods. Because of the flowers' calming, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, antibacterial, and antispasmodic qualities, they have been utilized for ages. In the past, chamomile infusion was used to treat insomnia, nightmares, hysteria, and other sleep issues as well as to soothe nerves and lower anxiety. Externally, chamomile was used to soften the skin of babies, as well as to treat abscesses, female furuncles, hemorrhoids, and genital disorders. It was also used for wounds that had not healed completely.

A monograph called "Shennong's Classic of Materia Medica" documents the use of Traditional Chinese Medicine by humans to treat a variety of ailments early in the Eastern Han Dynasty in China. According to the Traditional Chinese Medicine literature, chamomile has a variety of applications. Uyghur medicine in China was the first to document the plant in detail. "Bamu Nai" is the name given to chamomile in the tenth century Uyghur medical text known as the "Zhu Medical Canon." It smells and tastes a little bitter. The plant

provides nourishment for the stomach and nerves. It increases hunger, reduces uncomfortable swellings and sweating, and is commonly used to treat urinary system abnormalities, chronic headaches, constipation, poor sweating, and joint swelling. Some of the plants most commonly recognized for its traditional therapeutic applications is *M. chamomilla*. The parts of the plant (stem, leaves, flower, and entire plant) and the methods of preparation (decoction, infusion, vapor inhalation, bath, and compress) determine how *M. chamomilla* is commonly used.

The flowers of *Matricaria chamomilla* (Babonj/Babounj) are the most used portion of the plant in traditional Moroccan medicine, according to multiple research from various locations. The leaves and entire plant are next in line. For the treatment of diabetes, neurological diseases, angina, diarrhea, canker sores, abscesses, infections, and painful menstruation, it is made as an infusion or decoction. *Matricaria chamomilla* is used as an infusion in Spain to treat a number of illnesses, including as kidney stones, abdominal disorders, gastralgia, and female genital infections. Other uses for the plant include antiseptic, antiemetic, anti-inflammatory (for intestinal and stomach problems), sedative, and eye irritation. In Portugal, *Matricaria chamomilla* flowering top is used to treat a variety of illnesses, such as sciatic pain and infections of the skin, mouth, throat, and ear. In Turkey, the infusion is used as a sedative, to treat colds, and to prevent colic spasms. In Italian traditional medicine, *Matricaria chamomilla* has been used extensively to treat irritation, sprains, broken bones, and muscular-intestinal pain. Additionally, it has been used to bleach hair, tint it yellow, and act as a sedative. In Serbia, *Matricaria chamomilla* infusion is used to combat inflammation of the skin and mucous membranes, burns, stomach and vaginal problems, and liver problems. The infusion also serves as an aroma for shampoos and is utilized for mouth, eye, and skin care. *Matricaria chamomilla* is used in Greece to treat a variety of skin issues, eye infections, and gastrointestinal illnesses. In south-eastern Albania the uses *Matricaria chamomilla* tea to alleviate intestinal discomfort, diarrhea, and cough. The herb is used in Bulgaria to treat colds, genital swelling, swollen eyes, sore throats, and facial washing.

CONCLUSION:

The plant *Matricaria chamomilla* has been used as a natural treatment since ancient times. Because it includes a variety of bioactive phytochemicals with strong multimodal therapeutic effects, it is still widely utilized now and most likely will be in the future. The traditional medicine of China, Germany, Rome, Greece, and other nations makes

extensive use of chamomile. Because of its many therapeutic uses and pharmacological qualities, chamomile is in high demand on the global market. Because many herbal medications are easy to obtain, thought to be beneficial, and provide cash, there has also been a rise in the usage of natural ingredients greater than synthetic drugs.

In this review, we discussed the taxonomy and synonyms of *Matricaria chamomilla*, as well as its botanical and geographic distribution, phytochemistry, pharmacological qualities, ethnomedicinal use, therapeutic potential, and other uses. Chamomile essential oil was mostly composed of chamazulene, bisabolone oxide, bisalolol oxide A, α -bisabolol oxide B, bisabolol oxide B, and β -farnesene. There are low amounts of minerals like magnesium, potassium, calcium, zinc, and cadmium, polyacetylenes, flavonoids (like apigenin and quercetin), coumarins (such as umbelliferone and herniarin). Properties of *Matricaria chamomilla*'s pharmacology were It also has anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, antifungal, cancer-fighting, antidiabetic, antiparasitic, antipyretic, osteoporosis-fighting, and analgesic qualities. Diabetes, disorders of the neurological system, angina, abscess, diarrhea, canker sore, microbiological infections, anti-inflammatory, painful menstruation, antiseptic, sciatic pain, ear, throat, and skin, and stomach ailments are among the many conditions it is used to treat. F. Safety and efficacy make *Matricaria chamomilla* a viable herbal remedy. The potential for chamomile cultivation as an industrial and commercial medical crop in India seems promising. Promoting chamomile as a commercial crop is essential due to its high price on the global market, primarily for the export of chamomile oil from India.

REFERENCES:

1. Ali Esmail Al-Snafi, Lawahidh Fali Hasham. Bioactive constituents and pharmacological importance of *Matricaria chamomilla*: A recent review. GSC Biological and Pharmaceutical Sciences [Internet]. 2023 Feb 28 [cited 2024 Aug 4];12:2320–882. Available from: <https://ijcrt.org/papers/IJCRT2404970>.
2. Urolagin D, Aashif Raza A, Panda S. PHARMACOGNOSTIC AND PHARMACOLOGICAL REVIEW OF MATRICARIA CHAMOMILLA . 2024 [cited 2025 Aug 4];12:2320–882. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3210003/>.
3. Singh O, Khanam Z, Misra N, Srivastava M. Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.): An overview. Pharmacognosy Reviews [Internet]. 2011;5(9):82. Available from: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC3210003/>.
4. Akram W, Ahmed S, Mohd Rihan, Arora S, Khalid M, Ahmad S, et al. An updated comprehensive review of the therapeutic properties of Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.). International Journal of Food Properties. 2023 Dec 21;27(1):133–64. [An updated comprehensive review of the therapeutic properties of Chamomile \(Matricaria chamomilla L.\)](#).
5. Dai YL, Li Y, Wang Q, Niu FJ, Li KW, Wang YY, et al. Chamomile: A Review of Its Traditional Uses, Chemical Constituents, Pharmacological Activities and Quality Control Studies. Molecules. 2022 Dec 23;28(1):133; [Chamomile: A Review of Its Traditional Uses, Chemical Constituents, Pharmacological Activities and Quality Control Studies - PubMed](#)
6. El Mihaoui A, Esteves da Silva JCG, Charfi S, Candela Castillo ME, Lamarti A, Arnao MB. Chamomile (*matricaria chamomilla* L.): A review of ethnomedicinal use, phytochemistry and pharmacological uses. Life [Internet]. 2022 Mar 25;12(4):479. Available from: <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC9032859>
7. Bepari Abdulrazaq, Raj V, B VK, Boakye DA, Ramakrishnan S. The Cultivation of Chamomile (*Matricaria chamomilla* L.) in India: Insights into Origin, Distribution, and Germplasm Availability for Effective Farming Practices. Journal of Scientific Research and Reports. 2024 Dec 28;30(12):739–55. [The Cultivation of Chamomile \(Matricaria chamomilla L.\) in India: Insights into Origin, Distribution, and Germplasm Availability for Effective Farming Practices](#)
8. Unnati Soho, Pandey P, Raja W. A Review of Ethnomedicinal Use, Phytochemistry and Pharmacological Uses: *Matricaria chamomilla* L. [Internet]. 2024. p. 2024. Available from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/381489403_A_Review_of_Ethnomedicinal_Use_Phytochemistry_and_Pharmacological_Uses_Matricaria_chamomilla_L
9. Saeedi M, Khanavi M, Shahsavari K, Manayi* A. *Matricaria chamomilla*: an Updated Review on Biological Activities of the Plant and Constituents. Research Journal of Pharmacognosy [Internet]. 2024 Jan 1;11(1):109–36. Available from: <https://www.rjpharmacognosy.ir/article-183825.html>
10. A Review Article On “*Matricaria Chamomilla* (German Chamomile).” Tattu Anuja, Dalvi Apeksha, Latambale Komal, Walkunde Anushka, Shelke Suchitra - Bing [Internet]. Bing. 2022 [cited 2025 Aug 8]. https://www.bing.com/search?q=A+Review+Article+On+%E2%80%9CMatricaria+Chamomilla+%28German+Chamomile%29.%E2%80%9D++Tattu+Anuja%2C++Dalvi+Apeksha%2C+Latambale+Komal%2C+Walkunde+Anushka%2C+Shelke+Suchitra&form=ANSP_H1&refig=aeb619bdfab94d2fbcc0a6cb42537a6b&pc=HCTS